

Independent Review of Adult Disability Payment

**Our 'Call for
Evidence'
response**

2024

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Context: The Scottish Government invited responses to their 'Call for Evidence' for the Independent Review of Adult Disability Payment. The following text presents our response on behalf of the University of the West of Scotland.

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Take-up of Adult Disability Payment

Take-up for seldom heard groups

Our study data reflects insight from women who *did* apply for ADP. However, they did not reflect on their decision-making process, and observed the decision-making process of others. Several key factors were identified:

Women were not aware that PMDD was regarded as a disability and hence unaware that they could apply for support. The road to diagnosis for people with PMDD is known to be challenging, due to lack of health professional awareness around diagnosis and treatment (Osborn et al, 2020), and 'medical gaslighting' of women's mental health conditions (Khan et al, 2024). On average, it takes 12-20 years to receive an accurate diagnosis of PMDD (Chan et al, 2023; Osborn et al, 2020). Women describe this journey through the healthcare system as exhausting and traumatizing. This may influence their reluctance to embark on an ADP application process.

Women described how the stigma around mental health and also women's health made them reluctant to apply. Another important factor was not being aware that fluctuating conditions, such as PMDD, were eligible for ADP.

....Participant quote: "I think it just emphasises how physical illnesses and ailments are seen as more important, as for want of a better word, really than like mental symptoms, really. And also women's health as well, because it's... it's women's mental health, I think it's just lower down the priority sadly than other illnesses and everything."

.... Participant quote: "The first time I filled it in, still felt a lot of stigma about it, and I'm a very private person, and I don't sort of share very much about my experience with it, just because people don't understand. And I... so I didn't have anyone that could sort of advocate on my behalf or... or submit... you know, it says on the back, 'get your friends and family to write things in support.' Well I don't wanna ask them that, you know? I don't want to ask people to take part in what is a very private issue for me. So I think that's also something to... I wonder if, you know, the more evidence you provide, the more they believe you."

.... Participant quote: "But I think, you know, with fluctuating illnesses, maybe you know, you're paid monthly. So ten days out that month, you know, are you affected that poorly wif your mental health in that time? I think that's fair. Or two weeks, (Stutters) It's saying it's no' means tested, but you are challenged if, if you go tae work, you know, 'how can you manage to go tae work if you can't get dressed,' you know, if you're no' washing and bathing. But it's supposed to be it just affects you on these certain days, you know? So there is a lot o' tweaks that should be... and I think, you know, if you are putting down PMDD, they should have a wee bit more compassionate view towards you, you know, because you... you do, you're in that kinda low self- esteem mode, you don't want tae fight for it, you know, I've been there."

Some women didn't believe they could survive the ADP application process. They described how living with a debilitating mental health condition was exhausting. PMDD is characterised by cyclical symptoms that impact every menstrual cycle (typically 400+ cycles in a lifetime). Symptoms include rapid onset of severe depression, anxiety and suicidal ideation, accompanied by rapid changes in cognitive function that impact thought processes and decision-making (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). After each monthly episode women describe a tiring recovery phase before the next cycle begins.

..... Participant quote: "you know, especially wi' PMDD, I think definitely the PMDD, you're affected for more than ten days most o' the time. You know, even if that's if you're not having symptoms on they days, it's like the kinda aftermath o' that, isn't it, that you're recovering from. And the low self-esteem, you know, it does definitely affect ye more than fortnightly, PMDD. But trying tae, trying tae you know convince people o' that is, is very hard. So if, if that would be something tae put at, then you know, it affects you if your... your illness affects you for more than ten days you should be allowed, rather than every day as, as they see it, you know?"

They described the challenge of completing forms, contacting health professionals and advocating for themselves while navigating PMDD.

..... Participant quote: "I was a total mess, and I couldn't even write the form. So a woman came round to my house and I was like actually a mess, like I was like... I had really bad self-harm and when she came in, I think she tried to do the form with me for like an hour and a half the first time, and then I just was like not able to be with another person. So she left, and then she came back and did it again."

REFERENCES

American Psychiatric Association. Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Psychiatric Disorders, fifth edition. 2013.

Chan, K., Rubtsova, A.A. & Clark, C.J. Exploring diagnosis and treatment of premenstrual dysphoric disorder in the U.S. healthcare system: a qualitative investigation. *BMC Women's Health* 23, 272 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-023-02334-y>

Khan, K., Tariq, N. ul S. ., & Majeed, S. (2024). Psychological Impact of Medical Gaslighting on Women: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Professional & Applied Psychology*, 5(1), 110–125. <https://doi.org/10.52053/jpap.v5i1.249>

Osborn, E., Wittkowski, A., Brooks, J. et al. Women's experiences of receiving a diagnosis of premenstrual dysphoric disorder: a qualitative investigation. *BMC Women's Health* 20, 242 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-020-01100-8>

Evidence about pre-application support

None of our participants were aware of the support services. This suggests the services need better promotion. It is important that the services are promoted in an accessible way, to reach those that need it most. For example, our data focuses on women with PMDD, which can cause them to socially isolate themselves whilst also living with intrusive thoughts and suicidality. Attempting to reach them via accessible promotion strategies (e.g. TV, radio or social media adverts) may help people get the support they need. to those who need it.

..... Participant quote: "I feel like it's [info re: preapplication support] like all like veiled under this cloak of secrecy, and like nobody really knows and then sometimes you manage to find a good feed online, or like a TikTok that suddenly like helps. But that shouldn't really be up to chance, that you're able to like get that information, I feel like it should be there next to the like 'stop smoking' posters, like you know, 'here's support for, if you want to get this, and here's the information...' So that it's not just like those who know about it can apply for it. Because I was the same, like I... I should've applied for it a long time ago, but I onl... I only got it recently. Like last year. But I could've been having it for like the last fifteen years. So it's like... it's frustrating, and I know that P08_2RFP that echoes kind of what you were saying. And I think, yeah, just like that sharing of information, having like accessible information, so that somebody like your friend in their 70s, like they've... they can read it if they're not on TikTok. But then also a young person who needs to understand it can read it, so it's so they... like and they need to have this campaign, I know they're probably not going to... well I can't bring my own... like I don't think they would put any money into having a campaign, but they need to like share it as far and wide as they can. And they don't. And it feels like they put more money into catching people out and paying companies to do all these assessments, rather than trying to support people who actually need help.

..... Participant quote: "So I wasn't aware of that [preapplication support services]. It's not on any of the Social Security documents. It's not on anything that's come through the door. So I got in touch with them. But I'm also a bit sceptical, because they're employed by the Scottish Government, like I don't know if it's my PMDD paranoia or if I'm gonna feel like I'm gonna have to do the whole performative thing, like be on my best behaviour with them because they're employed by the Scottish Government. Yeah, I don't know about the transparency."

Approaching other sources of support

The evidence base for PMDD suggests several factors may influence how people with PMDD seek support.

Firstly, the symptoms of PMDD lead people to believe they 'do not deserve help', they are 'not worthy of support', they are a 'burden' to people' (Osborn et al, 2020). They, therefore, do not know always know that they need support.

Secondly, throughout their journey to diagnosis, our participants had asked for help and support from many people over many years. This was typically met with repeated refusal, or invalidation of their symptoms. Women spoke about the fear of asking for support and did not get it. This aligns with previous research about help-seeking experiences of people with PMDD in different countries (Chan et al, 2023; Osborn et al, 2020).

Thirdly, people's ability to complete the application paperwork is a factor influencing them seeking support.

..... Participant quote: "I think one of the, one of the main things is that like I had support filling out the application, of somebody who had like supported other people. And just even the task, like if you consider even the task of like filling out all the information as a daily living activity is like impossible, without the important support of other people. And that like cultural capita of like what is required, like all these insider tips of like what is required in order to communicate our symptoms and our struggles in a way that's palatable for the form."

Finally, loss of funding is an important issue impacting the provision of support services. Our study's co-researcher (sociolegal researcher and lecturer) previously worked as a welfare rights officer for Renfrewshire Citizens Advice Bureau. Their role, funded by the Scottish Legal Aid Board, was to provide support and representation for people applying for DLA/PIP/ADP. The loss of this funding significantly reduced the support available to people living in the Paisley and surrounding areas, an area of socioeconomic disadvantage (www.simd.scot).

Impact of processing times

Women with PMDD described the wait for decision as debilitating.

.... Participant quote: "I felt that I've had to fight for it, because sometimes, you know, if they have phoned me I've not felt up to it, you know, you've got that low self-esteem. So it's like trying to empower yourself at times, you know, that's what I've had to do. Even though it's taken every ounce of confidence and self-esteem to actually do it, and then when you've done it, you're like 'oh my God...' You don't know if you're going to get it for another six months' time. It's so debilitating."

Communications about decisions and re-determinations

There was consensus in our study about the quality of information shared with applicants. Participants described the decisions and/or decision letters not aligning with their recollection of the assessment, and that letters were poorly worded and lacking in empathy.

.... Participant quote: "The letter said that 'I laughed' so was clearly not depressed. But the lassie [the assessor], this was on zoom during lockdown, heard the doorbell go and made a joke about that always happening and I just politely laughed in reply, and yeah, that got used against me. It was disgusting."

.... Participant quote: "The award decision letter for me was the most unfair part, because it didn't align with the evidence that I and other people had provided, and also like the assessment, like the telephone assessor. And the dream scenario would be that there's a PMDD specialist that can be contacted, to like verify just how awful... even though symptoms can fluctuate, just how like awful they are, and how much they do impact daily living. So yeah, so PM- internal PMDD advocacy to whatever department that makes the overall decisions but we know that's like perhaps a wee bit idealistic and maybe not practical."

..... Participant quote: "I was surprised by my outcome. I don't think my out- even though my outcome was better than some people's, I don't think it fully captured the extent of like my needs, or the... or my support requirements. Yeah, it's wei- it's weird currently changing from PIP to ADP. And I am slightly concerned at how Social Security Scotland present themselves as like their values of like respect, integrity and the rest of it, 'cause I'm not sure if they actually live up to that, so... yeah. A wee bit overwhelmed about going through the reassessment process, just 'cause I know how unlikely it is that the PMDD is gonna be taken seriously. But I think it might work in my favour that I have other conditions. But again, I'm worried that the PMDD will be like sidelined."

In 2021, the Scottish Government launched the *Trauma Informed Practice Toolkit*. The aim of the toolkit is to "ensure that our services are delivered in ways that reduce barriers and prevent further harm or retraumatisation for those who have experienced psychological trauma or adversity at any stage in their lives." Insight from people who have applied for ADP suggests that the process and all communications are not aligned with trauma informed care. People with mental disorders (including PMDD) have a significantly higher prevalence of past trauma than people without a mental disorder (McKay et al, 2021; Slavich and Irwin, 2014). Trauma informed processes can help reduce the risk of further harm to vulnerable individuals seeking support from the welfare system. ADP processes should align with the Scottish Government's trauma informed toolkit.

REFERENCES

McKay MT, Cannon M, Chambers D, Conroy RM, Coughlan H, Dodd P, Healy C, O'Donnell L, Clarke MC. Childhood trauma and adult mental disorder: A systematic review and meta-analysis of longitudinal cohort studies. *Acta Psychiatr Scand*. 2021 Mar;143(3):189-205. doi: 10.1111/acps.13268

Slavich GM, Irwin MR. From stress to inflammation and major depressive disorder: a social signal transduction theory of depression. *Psychol Bull*. 2014 May;140(3):774-815. doi: 10.1037/a0035302.

Influences on re-determination and appeal rates

Insight from our participants England, applying for PIP, demonstrated several factors which *may* resonate with the ADP process. These included exhaustion, shame, lack of support from clinicians to provide letters, and lack of self-belief. Several described how the initial process made them feel suicidal so it would be a difficult decision to “go through that again”. One participant described how they lost a friend to suicide after he received an unsuccessful decision letter. This influenced her decision to not apply again.

We have insight from one participant in Scotland ...

..... Participant quote: “So when I initially got it, it wasn't for PMDD, it was for depression and anxiety, ... it's just all over the place. So I got it for that. And then when I stopped drinking completely, going into my 40s and everything, my [PMDD] symptoms were horrendous, absolutely horrendous. So when it came round, you know, I think it's every two years you've got to reapply for it, so I had to go to a clinic in Glasgow, and basically there was a woman there, she was a nurse and she was... and I was well-kempt, ..., I was just the way I was myself. But my mum had come in wi' me that day. And it wasn't one o' my worst days and, and I was that way, as you say, you're trying no' tae show how bad things really are, in a stupid kinda way because I didnae want them tae think I was stupid, I wanted them to think that I was actually doing things to try and help myself as well. And I thought, 'oh they might...' You know, I don't know what I thought, but stupidly I come away, and then I got the letter in saying I wasnae getting anything, I had good communication skills, which you can have some days, you know? So basically the reason I got it the next time, because I went to the tribunal, I seen all the points that I didnae get it for, and I says, “well I'm going tae have to really go hard on the points that I didn't get it for.” And the points that I didn't get it for were reasons that I should've got it. So I kind of had tae really... I think the reason I got it, you know, at the tribunal is because I took my poor wee mum in wi' me, and she was sitting next to me. My sister had basically died by suicide through alcoholism, like ten years before that. And she used to always speak about the anxiety and all these kinda things. And I think they actually took sympathy on my mum and that was the only reason I got it, to be fair. And then two years later I got another – I had to reapply for it again – and I got an English girl on the phone. And I asked for the transcript o' how, how the points were managed. And I had, I managed to get it, but just by the, you know, the kinda thing wi' my teeth again. Because I knew, I kind of I knew at this point how tae kinda work it, unfortunately. Do you know what I mean? The questions they ask ...So it's all there tae kind of trick you not to get it. So I says after that time, I says “I don't think I would put in for it again”

Can you provide specific examples of factors that may influence whether a person will appeal an Adult Disability Payment decision?

Some participants described how they had 'heard bad things' about the appeal process. Some of this had been via the media and some from hearing individual stories. One of our participants described her experience.

.... Participant quote: "it has been absolutely horrendous, because I ended up I had to go to a tribunal. Because... and the tribunal was horrendous, even though they gave me it, but I had to go in, and you know, I had to go in and look as though I had greasy hair, bags under my eyes and everything, so they could actually believe me. Because we can actually look all right, you know, on the outside. Most of my symptoms are internal. So it's terrible that you have to go to they lengths, you know, when you're going in tae a kinda interview tae, tae be accepted for benefits to help my condition."

Is there any other evidence you would like to share with us on the delivery of Adult Disability Payment to date?

Fluctuating conditions, such as PMDD, require a reformed approach for application and assessment. Our study identified several other factors for consideration.

Assessment of fluctuating conditions: there is a significant difference if/when assessing an applicant on their best versus worst day. This suggests an informed assessment process is needed and an awareness of how different conditions (such as PMDD) can vary over time. If an applicant is assessed on a 'good day' there is no reflection of the severity of their condition.

Lack of uniform systems: The administration and logistics of obtaining health reports from clinicians or others is a barrier to the process. Systems and services that 'speak to each other' may improve the efficiency of the application process both for applicants and staff.

Trained/specialist assessors: It is challenging for assessors to be trained on all medical conditions, however, increased awareness and training of certain disorders may be required to assess all applicants with equal opportunity. Our study focused on PMDD. PMDD is an internationally recognised mental disorder, typically clinically diagnosed by a GP, psychiatrist or gynaecologist. However, our study indicates a subjective approach by assessors (e.g. "despite my doctors diagnosis and letter, and me clearly struggling, the assessor wrote in my decision letter that I was able to look on Facebook so could function fine). One participant suggested 'specialised' assessors in the area of women's health, or women's mental health, to improve the fairness and quality fo assessments.

Please additional context

My co-researcher and I were funded by the Royal Society of Edinburgh to explore the experience of people applying for welfare benefits while living with the fluctuating condition Premenstrual Dysphoric Disorder (PMDD). PMDD is a severe hormone-based mood disorder that causes debilitating psychological symptoms in the latter half of the menstrual cycle. The majority of people with PMDD experience suicidal ideation, 1 in 2 self-harm and 1 in 3 attempt suicide.

We held three focus groups, in total gathering insight from 17 people living with PMDD (16 women and 1 non-binary participant). Of the 17, 13 lived in England and shared their experience of applying for PIP. Four were from Scotland and shared their experience of applying for ADP. The data included in our consultation response focuses on the ADP responses.

All four Scottish participants identified as women, age range 20-49, and all were clinically diagnosed with PMDD. Two women successfully received ADP on their first application and two were successful after mandatory reconsideration. Our findings have been submitted to the funder as a final report, and are in the process of being published as two separate articles in peer-reviewed academic journals.